

Efforts to Overcome the Threat of Terrorism by the Philippine Government in Maintaining The Integrity of the Nation

Yudi Rusmanto¹, Newman Sango²

^{1,2} Peace and Conflict Resolution, Faculty of National Security, Indonesia Defense University

ABSTRACT: Terrorism is often used as a means to achieve political goals, power, religious interests, and other similar ends. Terrorism is a form of threat that can lead to acts of violence, destruction, and chaos as a violation of the law generally carried out in a targeted and planned manner. The Philippines is one of the countries that has become a strategic target for terrorist acts. The threat of the theoretical group cannot be separated from the condition of the Philippine government which is not yet structurally and intellectually strong in dealing with this threat. In this paper, the author wants to examine the form of the threat of terrorism which is a serious nuisance to the security of the Philippines. So that it can be seen whether the increasing threat of terrorists in the Philippines is in line with the readiness of the government to deal with these threats. This research method uses a qualitative description. By focusing on the existing problems described descriptively, namely by using a qualitative method to make descriptive results able to form concepts in the form of more objective results. The short result of the research is that the largest terrorist group in the Philippines is Abu Sayyaf. As the seeds of terrorism in the Philippines started from the struggle of the Moro nation in seeking asylum for independence, it changed from an Islamic political movement, namely the National Liberation Front (MNLF) and then in the 80s it split into a more radical Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF), and that utilized by the ASG group (Abu Sayyaf Group). Both the MNLF and MILF deny ties to the Abu Sayyaf group. The two have officially distanced themselves because of his attacks on civilians and his alleged profiteering.

KEYWORDS: Terrorism, Abu Sayyaf, Philippines, Efforts to Overcome the Threat of Terrorism

I. INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is a large archipelagic nation with more than 7,000 islands and a 36,289 km² long coastline (Larasati, A. 2015). Due to the Philippines' position as an archipelagic nation, which has a small land size of only 30,000 km² and no land boundaries, the majority of the country's access points are via ocean channels (Mendoza, L. R. 2014). Therefore, border control and marine security are two crucial factors and present a difficulty in the Philippines' fight against terrorism. The rise of terrorism in the Philippines has not diverged significantly from that of other Southeast Asian nations like Indonesia.

The majority of people in the Philippines are Catholic, and the southern Philippines has long been the scene of terror attacks and uprisings by the Moro people, who are actually Muslims and seek to secede from the Philippines. The Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF), which has been in charge of the insurgency movement since the 1970s, was followed in the 1980s by the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF), a division of the more radical MNLF, as its leader. Then, in the 1990s, the two preceding movements split off, creating the Abu Sayyaf Group on a distinct spectrum (Eusaquito, M. P. 2004). The ASG, also known as the Islamic State of

Iraq and Syria - Province of the Philippines, a separatist group composed of militias based around the southern islands of the Philippines, including Jolo, Basilan, and Mindanao, has taken advantage of the spectrum of radicalism that the MILF has guaranteed as an insurgency. As a result, it is also possible to assert that the number of transnational terrorist acts in Indonesia directly correlated with the end of the protracted battle in the Southern Philippines and the outcome of the Southern Philippines' insurgency camps being shut down (Eusaquito, M.P. 2004).

All political groups fighting for the independence of the Moro Nation, including the Abu Sayyaf Group and the MNLF or MILF, feel wronged by the Philippine government. Based on the claim made by the Philippine Military that the Abu Sayyaf receives backing from both parties. The Philippine government is aware of the seriousness of the threat posed by terrorist groups there as well as the significant influence that terrorists wield there. The main threat that the Philippines is concerned about is related to transnational terrorists, who transfer knowledge and expertise in terror-related activities to local terrorist organizations in order to support their capacity to commit acts of terror, particularly in terms of financial assistance for operational cooperation between these terrorist organizations.

II. DISCUSSION

The research method and framework in this paper aim to determine the factors or forms of threats that become serious disturbances such as the security of the Philippines. Furthermore, the purpose of this study is to determine whether the form of terrorist threat in the Philippines is in line with the preparedness of countermeasures from the security forces in dealing with these threats. As is the case with the Philippine government's program in eradicating acts of terror in the Philippines, such as the acts of the Abu Sayaf terrorists, the MILF insurgency movement, and others.

In analyzing the authors use a conceptual framework. The method used in this research is descriptive which aims to describe a symptom, event, or event that is happening at the present time. This method is used to explain how the Philippine government carries out its government program to tackle the actions of terrorist groups. Limitation The problem of this research is the problem that focuses on the efforts of the Philippine government in overcoming the efforts of terrorist groups, especially on the islands of Mindanao and Sulu. The handling and counter-terrorism of extreme theoretic groups such as the Abu Sayyaf and its networks.

The results of this study include the Philippines' national security policy in counter-research obtained from the results of a one-week study in the Philippines study with online information collection and zoom meeting seminar review sources on terrorists in the Philippines. The Philippines is still in the early stages of developing its capacity and capability in terms of counter-terrorism.

A. The Case and Motive of Terrorism in the Philippines, what competent institutions are handling terrorism and Counter-terrorism in the Philippines

In the Philippines, terrorism is a significant social problem that is associated with the Moro conflict and communist uprising, both of which aim to break away from the Republic of the Philippines (Mendoza et al. 2021). Since March 1968, there has been an insurgency known as the Moro conflict in the Philippines' Mindanao area that has involved numerous armed organizations (Gross, 2007). The Moro war has its roots in the Bangsamoro people's long history of resistance to foreign domination, particularly the American annexation of the Philippines in 1898. To date, Moro has continued to oppose the Philippine government (Gutierrez, & Borrás, 2004). Political tensions and outright conflicts between the Philippine government and the Moro Muslim rebel group grew during the rule of Philippine dictator Ferdinand Marcos (Twemlow et al, 2001). The Jabidah massacre on March 18, 1968, which resulted in the deaths of 60 Filipino Muslim commandos on their way to retake the eastern half of the Malaysian state of Sabah, served as the catalyst for the Moro rebellion (Bueno, & Salapa, 2021).

The Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF), an armed insurgent group dedicated to establishing an independent Mindanao, was founded by University of the Philippines lecturer professor Nur Misuari in 1972 after numerous organizations pushing for Moro self-rule had been established. These organizations did not last

for a long time (George, 1980). The Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF), which aimed to create an Islamic state within the Philippines, was one of the MNLF's many offshoots that formed before their scheduled split. A section led by Emeril Umbra Kato opposed when the MILF changed its aspirations from independence to autonomy in late 2008, leading to the creation of the Bangsamoro Islamic Freedom Fighters (BIFF) in 2010.

The Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF), an armed insurgent group dedicated to establishing an independent Mindanao, was founded by University of the Philippines lecturer professor Nur Misuari in 1972 after numerous organizations pushing for Moro self-rule had been established. These organizations did not last for a long time (George, 1980). The Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF), which aimed to create an Islamic state within the Philippines, was one of the MNLF's many offshoots that formed before their scheduled split. A section led by Emeril Umbra Kato opposed when the MILF changed its aspirations from independence to autonomy in late 2008, leading to the creation of the Bangsamoro Islamic Freedom Fighters (BIFF) in 2010. Public transportation and other meeting places, such as street markets, have been targeted, but the groups—most notably Abu Sayyaf and the Rajah Solaiman Movement, two organizations that have taken credit for the majority of the attacks—have also engaged in widespread kidnappings and shootings.

Terrorist organizations have the desire and ability to carry out attacks anywhere in the nation, especially in the capital Manila, on places of worship, public transportation (including airports and the metro system), shopping malls, and entertainment venues. Small weapons and improvised explosive devices, both personnel- and vehicle-borne, have been used in attacks. This is done with the intention of maintaining pressure on the government to comply with their demands (Mendoza et al, 2021). Recent major events include: on June 28, 2019, a dual suicide attack on a military base in Indanan, Sulu Province, killed 3 civilians and 3 military personnel in addition to the 2 attackers, and on August 24, 2020, two explosions in Jolo, Sulu, resulted in a number of deaths and injuries. On January 27, 2019, an additional 22 people suffered injuries. On December 31, 2018, bombs exploded at a Roman Catholic cathedral on Jolo Island in Sulu Province, killing 27 people and injuring dozens more. On January 27, 2019, an IED exploded at the entrance to the South Seas shopping mall in Cotabato City, killing 2 people and seriously injuring dozens more. In remote areas, armed confrontations between security personnel and extremist organizations happen frequently and without notice. Bystanders have been hurt in prior altercations. Rural places should be thoroughly researched before visiting. On May 9, 2022, elections for both the presidency and local offices are planned. Election-related violence, including terrorist attacks, has occurred in previous elections.

According to the Global Terrorism Index for 2019, the Philippines was among the top ten nations most adversely affected by terrorism. According to the aforementioned index, the Communist Party of the Philippines and the New People's Army (CPP-NPA) are the two deadliest terrorist organizations currently active in the Philippines, having been involved in 36% of all murders and 39% of all terrorist-related incidents and attacks against targets related to the police, military, and the government. The Philippines understands the need to holistically address the root causes of terrorism through a whole-of-government and whole-of-society approach while collaborating with intergovernmental organizations, civil society, communities, victims, and their families in order to effectively counterterrorism (Bueno, & Salapa, 2021).

The most recent attempt to combat terrorism and all associated activities while still maintaining the protection of our civil and political rights is the Anti-Terrorism Act of 2020. Border security, law enforcement, and legislation: The 2007 Human Security Act was replaced on July 3 with the Antiterrorism Act (ATA), which was signed into law by President Duterte. The ATA was created by the Philippine government with support from the US government and other governments in order to criminalize predicate acts, remove legal barriers to prosecuting terrorists, and give law enforcement more investigative resources. ATA critics have petitioned the Supreme Court to declare the law illegal out of concern that it could be used against political opponents and human rights advocates. Human rights organizations claim that government officials identify activists and other individuals as terrorists in an effort to stifle opposition to the government or intimidate them in local conflicts. Many of these people are subsequently murdered or targeted by allegedly politically driven criminal accusations (Ragragio, 2021).

Anti-terrorism financing legislation is included in the nation's legislative framework. ISIS affiliates and the CPP/NPA were placed on the government's publicly available list of organizations that have been classified

as terrorist organizations. The Philippine National Police Special Action Force and other specialized law enforcement groups have benefited from investments in personnel and training, which have increased the government's ability to identify, discourage, and prevent terrorist actions. The government kept up its efforts in law enforcement and the legal system to combat terrorism, thwarting plots and looking into and convicting terrorists. On September 28, a regional court sentenced seven defendants to life in prison after finding them guilty of participating in a terrorist blast in 2016 that left 17 people dead at a night market in Davao City. Although ASG claimed responsibility for the attack and the attackers had connections to ASG and the Maute gang, prosecutors chose to prosecute the seven with murder due to flaws in the Human Security Act.

The government took steps to prevent terrorist travel and improved information exchange with overseas partners as part of the implementation of UNSCR 2396. Several FTFs were expelled by the Bureau of Immigration (BI) using exclusion and deportation powers. Though the BI conducted watchlist screenings at a few ports of entry, more capacity is required to gather passenger data and expand access to INTERPOL databases at other crucial ports of entry outside the Manila International Airport. The Philippines strengthened oversight programs, information exchange, and screening technology and training, as well as working more closely with international partners (Gunduz, 2021). The government has established and executed CVE training for security personnel and civil officials, as well as a National Action Plan on Preventing and Countering Violent Extremism. On CVE programs, local governments, NGOs, and the commercial sector collaborated. In order to promote departures from the ASG, BIFF, and the Maute Group as well as to rehabilitate former terrorist combatants, the Armed Forces of the Philippines collaborated with regional partners. In order to counter terrorist messaging, the government also backed strategic communications initiatives. GCERF provides funding for initiatives to prevent and combat violent extremism for local implementers around the Philippines (Ragragio, 2021).

B. The Government's Attention and the Role of the Philippine Government in Efforts to Respond to the Development and Actions of Terrorist Groups

The Muslim-majority Moro in the Southern Philippines have attempted to secede from the Philippines, which has a mainly Catholic population, and have terrorized or revolted against it for decades. The Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF), which has been in charge of this movement since the 1970s, was followed in the 1980s by the more extremist Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF). The two earlier movements in the 1990s led to the subsequent emergence of the Abu Sayyaf Group. The Southern Philippines is home to the small yet incredibly violent Abu Sayyaf faction. They attempted to establish an independent Islamic state in Western Mindanao and the Sulu region, where the Southern Philippines region is highest, through terrorism, independence, assassination, abduction, and extortion. The observation led to the conclusion that ASG (Abu Sayyaf Group) was founded as a group that employs criminal tactics because its members believed that criminality may produce quick results (immediate results).

It is impossible to isolate the effects of Southeast Asia's actions and strategies from what happened on November 9, 2011. The party believed to be in charge of the incident has been identified as the Al-Qaeda organization, which has been classified as a terrorist organization with a presence in Southeast Asia. With the goal of making other nations responsive and aware of emerging global threats, the United States is actively promoting the Global War on Terror. Representative and religious groups carry out a variety of uprisings throughout the countries of Southeast Asia; particularly, foreign terrorist organizations like Al-Qaeda exploit religion to expand their networks there.

The plans of the perpetrators of the Al-Qaeda group's attacks were carried out in a number of the attacks that occurred in Southeast Asian nations. The Bali Bombings in Indonesia in 2002, the bombing of the Philippine military base in Zamboanga in 2002, and the bombing of the airport in Davao City in 2003 were all allegedly carried out by the New People's Army (NPA), Jemaah Islamiyah, MILF, and Abu Sayyaf Group. In 2001, the Moro Islamic Liberation Front carried out a rebellion that resulted in the deaths of foreign tourists in the southern Philippines. The Philippines had the most terrorist attacks in Southeast Asia from the 1970s until 2018, according to data from the Global Terrorism Database. Based on the table below, the number of cases in the Philippines is the highest compared to other ASEAN member countries.

Tabel: Total Case Terrorism in South Asia area till 2013
Data from Giuliani Agustha Namora

No	Nama Negara	Jumlah Kasus
1	Filipina	988 Kasus
2	Thailand	766 Kasus
3	Indonesia	83 Kasus
4	Myanmar	36 Kasus
5	Kamboja	2 Kasus
6	Malaysia	15 Kasus
7	Laos	1 Kasus
8	Vietnam	-
9	Singapore	-
10	Brunei	-

According to the table above, there were 988 more cases in the Philippines than there were in Laos, which had just one case. Additionally, it was observed that Malaysia had 15 cases, Indonesia had 83 cases, Myanmar had 36 cases, and the final two cases made up the second-largest case. The movement known as the Abu Sayyaf was founded in Basilan. The beginning of the MNLF movement's collapse, during which Abdurajak Janjalani did not alter Nur Misuari's diplomatic strategies as the MNLF movement's head at the time, signified the formation of this group. The Abu Sayyaf gang engaged in bloody combat to realize its objective of creating an Islamic State in the Southern Philippines. The hostages were moved, taken hostage, and then killed by the Abu Sayyaf organization. Abdurajak Janjalani, who disputes that the MILF is an underground movement of the Abu Sayaf Group, supports the movement of the Abu Sayyaf Group as a terrorist organization that caused interreligious violence. Despite being a relatively tiny movement, the Abu Sayyaf group has been successful in disrupting the Philippines by carrying out bombs there. In the Philippines, where Catholicism predominates and Islam is the minority religion, the conflict being pushed by this organization is in fact an interreligious one.

The Philippines became the illustrious Sulu sultanate kingdom in that country, but from the standpoint of the Abu Sayyaf group, they formerly battled to deal with Moro Muslims from Christians. The Moro people struggle to see themselves represented in the Philippines because of this. The Abu Sayyaf gang seeks out this region by making Christians its enemies by intimidating them with violence because it feels neglected by the

people who are Christians. Assistance from nations outside the Philippines also contributes to the existence of the Abu Sayyaf organization. Al-Qaeda, a global terrorist organization, has provided financial support to the Abu Sayyaf organization.

The assistance by Al-Qaeda to Abu Sayyaf in growing its network. Anything that is funded by Al-Qaeda is what Abu Sayyaf requires. Additionally, all Abu Sayyaf groups receive funding from hostage ransom payments. Since severing ties with the MNLF (Moro Nation Liberation Front), Abu Sayyaf has abducted and held hostages both white and Filipino persons. The hostages were frequently killed, especially if they did not pay the demanded ransom. For instance, Malaysian tourist Bernard Ghen Ted Fen was killed in November 2015 after his family was unable to pay a ransom of 40 million Philippine pesos, which is equal to Rp. 12 billion. Abu Sayyaf's activities are primarily concentrated in southern Mindanao. In the Philippines, businesses affiliated with the Abu Sayyaf gang are attempting to make the Islamic State the dominant ideal. The Philippine government has proposed numerous answers, but this group refuses to accept them and instead favors violence.

Growing instances of piracy in nearby waters could make this area the "new Somalia." For concern that if security was not increased, piracy in the busy shipping routes on Indonesia's maritime border with the Philippines could reach levels comparable to those in Somalia. The seas are a part of a significant shipping route with an annual worth of \$40 billion US. Supertankers from the Indian Ocean that are too loaded down to navigate the Straits of Malacca use this passageway. Three separate attacks on barges in Philippine waters along the route by Abu Sayyaf organizations in the Philippines, which had ties to Al-Qaeda, resulted in the detention of 18 Indonesians and Malaysians. The kidnapping, beheading, raiding, and extortion organization Abu Sayyaf has requested 50 million pesos (\$1.1 million) in ransom to free Indonesia.

The existence of the Abu Sayyaf Group, which has a base in the southern islands of the Philippines, is one of the issues that the Philippine government feels has to be given serious consideration and needs to be dealt with together. The Abu Sayyaf Group stands out from other separatist organizations in the Philippines because its operations are typically more extreme. It is not surprising that the Abu Sayyaf Group is regarded as the most dangerous terrorist organization currently operating in Southeast Asia, and it can be argued that the separatist movement led by this organization has evolved into a problem that transcends national boundaries and may pose a security threat to the ASEAN region. The governments of the Philippines and the United States have made efforts to put an end to this movement, but due to the guerrilla tactics used by this organization, it is still challenging to destroy. From March 2002 through December 2006, the US government and other countries cooperated in counterterrorism (Rona OF, 2008).

In addition to the Philippines, the Abu Sayyaf gang also committed violent crimes and kidnappings in nearby nations like Malaysia and Indonesia. As a result, the activities of the Abu Sayyaf Group have expanded beyond national boundaries and now pose a risk to regional security in ASEAN. In an ideal world, regional organizations like ASEAN play a significant role in resolving issues. If members of international organizations can work together to solve problems, then problems can be effectively resolved. Southeast Asia's issues are getting worse, which makes ASEAN's role in their resolution more important. The Global Terrorism Database (GTD) records 11,453 wiretaps in the Southeast Asian region between 1970 and 2016. Because it necessitates cooperation between member nations to manage the ASEAN region, the subject of terrorism is one of the crucial ones that needs to be handled at the ASEAN level. At the 7th ASEAN Summit on November 5, 2001 in Brunei Darussalam, 10 ASEAN member countries confirmed ASEAN's efforts to overcome the area and adopted the ASEAN Joint Action for Counter-Terrorism.

Cooperation under the AMMTC (ASEAN Ministerial Meeting on Transnational Crime) system includes fighting terrorism. When the 12th ASEAN Summit was held in the Philippines on January 13, 2007, ASEAN also drafted the ASEAN Convention on Counter-Terrorism (ACCT) to further their collaboration. This convention is a crucial tool for ASEAN cooperation since it offers a solid legal foundation for further cooperation in the fight against terrorism.

The prevention and management of attacks using counterterrorism. According to Sandler, there are primarily two types of anti-terrorism policies: proactive and defensive. DE radicalization and disengagement are two strategies that might be used in the fight against terrorism. DE radicalization is a soft-spoken strategy that aims to soften the radical and uncompromising ideology of jihad while still promoting psychological recovery.

Disengagement is a soft-line strategy that aims to improve the social connections of ex-offenders, stop them from re-entering their network or society, and stop them from committing the same crime.

The Philippine government has a cohesive and integrated document on terrorism in terms of policies and institutions, but it also has a very extensive executive directive—at least on paper—in the form of laws and regulations. The aviation and maritime industries, which are in fact governed by international standards, are the most obvious in the Philippine government's efforts to toughen targets.

According to the Philippine government, the goal of terrorism is to persuade the public to fear and form large, unusual networks in order to pressure the government into granting their demands, which are in violation of the country's laws and constitution. The Philippine government has published a National Security document for the years 2011 through 2016 that focuses on the insurgency in Mindanao's two main groups as a security priority. According to the efforts at punishment, the Philippine military is spearheading military reprisal through a variety of operations to neutralize terrorist capabilities, with the police backing. Although the country's anti-terrorism law, which was just passed five years ago, exists, it has never been applied to prosecute terrorist activities due to a number of flaws.

According to the Anti-Terrorism Council-Program Management Center Institute at the Office of the President of the Philippines, the country already has an appropriate organizational structure, laws, and regulations, as well as a coordination chart between institutions, for countermeasures that are part of the country's national policies. However, these three things have not been proven to be true. This is made possible since the Philippines now lacks the human resources needed to participate in efforts to combat terrorism (Erwin Yusup Sitorus, 2016). The Philippine government's response to the accords reached thus far has been ad hoc and reactive, rather than strategic and decisive, due to a lack of resources (Eusaquito, M. P. 2004).

This coordination chart shows that, despite not performing as well as anticipated, the Philippine government is committed to combating terrorism in its nation. The chairman of NCTAG claims that in terms of fighting terrorism, the Philippine government is still gaining knowledge from both its partner, the United States, and the Indonesian government.

The threat of terrorism is highlighted in the Philippine government's National Security Policy document for the years 2011 to 2016 as the country's second top security concern after the rebel group in Mindanao. The Abu Sayyaf Group (SAG) and its global terrorist network, which includes JI, (Jamaah Islamiyah) are the terrorist organization that the Philippines considers to be the highest threat, according to A. F. (2010).

The previous administration, led by President Aquino III, outlined three main strategies for combating terrorism in the Philippines, namely:

- Security countermeasure, which entails safeguarding prospective targets. In this situation, intelligence is crucial.
- Put law enforcement into action to fight terrorism.
- By taking into account the socio-economic requirements of communities that are seen as susceptible, the recruitment of Filipino people to join terrorist organizations can be prevented.

Although the Philippine government views terrorism as a criminal activity, the military is the key force behind the country's efforts to combat terrorism. The police were initially tasked by the Philippine government with combating terrorism; however, this responsibility was later transferred to the military because it was believed that the scope of the threat posed by terrorism had grown, leaving the police with no other duties than to assist the military in dealing with insurgency and terrorists.

The police play a distinct role in the Philippine government's policy, which places an emphasis on counterterrorism or defensive actions against terrorists. The Philippine police developed a two-layered protection system called Target Hardening and Intelligence. The Philippine government places a high priority on improving intelligence by safeguarding vulnerable targets and bolstering reactions in post-attack recovery. Target hardening is a technique that the Philippine government is adopting by stepping up protection around terrorist targets. The aviation, maritime, public transportation, and vital infrastructure sectors are the focus of the target hardening initiatives the Philippine government is implementing as part of its national security strategies against terrorism.

In order to create a Transport Security Office under the Department of Transport and Communications, the Philippine government established the Philippine Transport Security Authority Act. Because of this, this agency is the only one in the Philippines with responsibility for transportation security and the duty to create, execute, and oversee the application of International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) standards.

Regarding the similarities with Indonesia in combating terrorism, the Philippines is still in desperate need of resources because neither Indonesia nor the Philippines have an adequate state capacity in terms of supervision and good governance, despite having a larger region and a larger population. The Philippine government has increased control over border management in order to combat terrorism. The only ways to enter and leave the Philippines are via ship or airplane. In addition, because the Philippines is an archipelagic nation with many islands, the country's sea boundary is regarded as being particularly open to intrusion, and the central government's capacity for monitoring and enforcing the law is still quite limited.

III. CONCLUSION

One of the Southeast Asian nations, the Philippines is made up of a vast archipelago with more than 7,000 islands and a coastline that stretches for over 36,289 kilometers. The Philippines' land area is not particularly large, and the country lacks land borders, hence most travel to and from the country takes place via sea. Therefore, border control and marine security are two crucial factors and present a difficulty in the Philippines' fight against terrorism. The Philippines are aware of the serious threat posed by both domestic terrorist groups and international terrorists operating there. The main threat posed by transnational terrorists to the Philippines is the dissemination of knowledge and expertise on how to commit acts of terrorism to local terrorist organizations so that they can support or facilitate domestic terrorist activities or operational cooperation between terrorist groups.

The Philippine government's approach to terrorism so far has tended to be ad hoc and reactive, rather than strategic and decisive, which makes the government's programs and legislative rules less than ideal due to a lack of resources. Created widespread and overwhelming terror and panic among the populace in an effort to force the government to accede to their unlawful demands. Although the Philippine government perceives terrorism as a criminal offense, the military serves as its main operational base in the country's war against terrorism. The military took over counterterrorism operations in the Philippines from the police after it was determined that the threat posed by terrorism had grown, leaving the police with no other role except to assist the military in combating the terrorist threat.

Due to the fact that the defense system is crucial to combating terrorism, particularly in terms of

bolstering intelligence, safeguarding vulnerable targets, and improving reactions and post-attack recovery. The Philippine government must carry out and put into practice specific and correct methods, particularly by bolstering human resources, in order to create legislation that will serve as a solid legal foundation for the country's fight against terrorism. Although in theory, the Philippines has established a law mandating the creation of an OTS under the Department of Transportation and Communications to combat terrorism in the country. This law is known as the Philippine Transportation Security Authority Act. This organization intends to be in charge of the Philippines' transportation safety as well as the application of the International Civil Aviation Organization's standards (ICAO). This is due to the fact that, as one of the biggest archipelagic nations, the Philippines is particularly susceptible to marine threats as a security sector.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bueno, D. C., & Salapa, A. C. (2021) The Philippine administrative system: A review of the past, present, and future research.
- [2] Eadie, P. E. (2011). Legislating for Terrorism: The Philippines' Human Security Act 2007. *Journal of Terrorism Research*.
- [3] George, T. J. (1980). *Revolt in Mindanao: The rise of Islam in Philippine politics*. Oxford University Press.
- [4] Gross, M. L. (2007). *A Muslim Archipelago: Islam and politics in Southeast Asia*. Defense Department.
- [5] Gunduz, K. A. (2021). Moving beyond a minimal democracy: A comparative analysis of reform episodes in non-consolidated democracies of Turkey, Mexico and the Philippines.
- [6] Gutierrez, E., & Borrás, S. M. (2004). *The Moro conflict: Landlessness and misdirected state policies*.
- [7] Human Rights Watch. (2015). *World report 2015: Events of 2014*. Policy Press.
- [8] Ragragio, J. L. D. (2021). Strongman, patronage and fake news: Anti-human rights discourses and populism in the Philippines. *Journal of Language and Politics*, 20(6), 852-872.
- [9] Mendoza, R. U., Ong, R. J. G., Romano, D. L. L., & Torno, B. C. P. (2021). Counterterrorism in the Philippines. *Perspectives on Terrorism*, 15(1), 49-64.
- [10] Niksch, L. (2007, January). Abu Sayyaf: Target of Philippine-US anti-terrorism cooperation. LIBRARY OF CONGRESS WASHINGTON DC CONGRESSIONAL RESEARCH SERVICE.
- [11] Twemlow, S. W., Fonagy, P., Sacco, F. C., Gies, M. L., Evans, R., & Ewbank, R. (2001). Creating a peaceful school learning environment: A controlled study of an elementary school intervention to reduce violence. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 158(5), 808-810.
- [12] I Made Adi Lesmana, Sukma Sushanti, Putu Titah Kawitri Resen.
- [13] Eusaquito, M. P. (2004). *The Philippine Respon to Terrorism: The Abu Sayyaf Group*.
- [14] Philippines, A. F. (2010). *Internal Peace and Security Plan*. Retrieved from <http://www.afp.mil.ph/pdf/IPSP%20Bayanihan.pdf>
- [15] Kerjasama politik keamanan ASEAN, www.kemlu.go.id/.../kerjasama%20politik%20keamanan%20ASEA. Diakses pada tanggal 09 Desember 2017
- [16] Giuliani Agustha Namora, "PERAN ASEAN CONVENTION ON COUNTER TERRORISM DALAM PENANGANAN TERORISME DI FILIPINA PERIODE 2011 – 2013", <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/135422-ID-none.pdf>, diakses pada tanggal 9 Maret 2018.
- [17] Avarusyd's blog, gerakan Abu sayyaf, <https://avarusyd.wordpress.com/2011/09/07/gerakan-abu-sayyaf/>.
- [18] BBC, Lima hal tentang kelompok abu sayyaf di Filipina, www.bbc.com/indonesia/dunia/2016/04/160411dunia_lima_hal_abu_sayyaf.
- [19] VOA, pemerintah: perairan asia tenggara bisa jadi Somalia baru, <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.voaindonesia.com/amp/3297926.html?espv=1>

-
- [20] Ulfah K.Y, R.B. Sularto, Oktober 2014 “Counter Terrorism bagi pelaku tindak pidana terorisme sebagai upaya penanggulangan kejahatan terorisme di indonesia”, Vol. 10 No. 1, <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://media.neliti.com/media/publication/107811IDnone.pdf&ved=2ahUKEwjK75fwkKDZAHVFRY8KHeyOA7sQFjACegQIExAB&usg=AOvVaw1aXOHL5aB6VqcoF9gIEvy5>.
- [21] http://catalogue.paramadina.ac.id/index.php?p=show_detail&id=22757
- [22] Eusaquito, M. P. (2004). *The Philippine Respon to Terrorism: The Abu Sayyaf Group*.
- [23] Erwin Yusup Sitorus, *Jurnal Prodi Peperangan Asimetris* | Juni 2017 | Volume 3 Nomor 2: kebijakan keamanan nasional filipina dalam kontra-terorisme the philippine national security policy in the counter terrorism, dalam file:///C:/Users/5285/Downloads/97-642-1-PB%20(1).pdf
- [24] S. Pusanathan, “Upaya ASEAN untuk memerangi terorisme”, <http://www.asean.org/15060.htm>
- [25] Eusaquito, M. P. (2004). *The Philippine Respon to Terrorism: The Abu Sayyaf Group*.
- [26] Metz, Steven (2001). *Asymmetry and U.S Strategy: Definition, Background, and Strategy Concepts*. US Army Strategic Studies Institute.
- [27] Larasati, A. (2015). *Kerjasama Keamanan Indonesia - Filipina dalam Mengataasi Masalah Terorisme Tahun 2005-2011*. Riau: Universitas Riau.
- [28] Mendoza, L. R. (2014). Retrieved Juni 22, 2016, from "Transportation Security in the Philippines 6th APEC Transportation Ministerial Meeting": <http://www.apectptwg.org.cn/.../Transportation%20Security%20Philippines>
- [29] Nasional, D. R. (2008). *Suatu Pemikiran Tentang Perang Asimetris*. Jakarta. Nugroho, R. D. (2004). *Kebijakan Publik (Formulasi, Implementasi dan Evaluasi)*. Jakarta: Elex Media Komputindo.
- [30] Ode, M. D. (2006). *Peran Militer dalam Ketahanan Nasional; Studi Kasus Bidang Hankam di Indonesia Tahun 1967 – 2000*. Jakarta: Pustaka Sinar Harapan.
- [31] Permatasari, A. (2013). *Penerapan Strategi Penggantaran dalam Upaya Penanggulangan Terorisme di Singapura, Malaysia, Filipina dan Indonesia*. Retrieved June 23, 2016, from [http://lib.ui.ac.id/file?file=digital/20334951-T33026-Anggalia%20Putri%20Permatasari.p df](http://lib.ui.ac.id/file?file=digital/20334951-T33026-Anggalia%20Putri%20Permatasari.pdf) Pertahanan,